

[white paper: pedagogical]

Diamond Open Access

[waiting peer review]

Goldbach Conjecture, Twin Primes Conjecture, and Bounded Gap Theorem in the Language of Number Theory

Open Mathematics Collaboration*†

September 3, 2021

Abstract

We write the formulas of the theorem and the conjectures highlighted in the title of this white paper in the language of number theory for pedagogical purpose in first-order logic.

keywords: Goldbach conjecture, bounded gap theorem, number theory language, first-order logic

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/u45y3/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5428990>

Introduction

1. This is a pedagogical white paper on *first-order logic*.
2. Our purpose is to discuss a result in [1] which is licensed under [2].
3. We use minimal notation but preserving all relevant mathematical information.

*All *authors* with their *affiliations* appear at the end of this white paper.

†Corresponding author: mplobo@uft.edu.br | **Open Mathematics Collaboration**

Meta-linguistic symbols

4. $:=$ means that what is on the left is defined by what is on the right.
5. \equiv means that the strings on both sides are identical.

The language of number theory

6.
$$\mathcal{L}_{NT} = \{0, S, +, \cdot, E, <\}$$
7. $0 :=$ number zero
8. $S(x) = x + 1 :=$ successor function
9. $+, \cdot, < :=$ usual binary operations
10. $E :=$ exponentiation (e.g. $E(3, 2) = 9$)
11. $\mathcal{L}_{NT} :=$ the language of number theory assumed to be interpreted with respect to $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$

Prime number

12. $n \in \mathbb{N}$
13. $\bar{n} := \underbrace{SS\dots SS}_n 0$
 n times
14. $\text{prime}(x) \equiv \bar{1} < x \wedge \neg(\exists y)(\exists z)[(y + \bar{2}) \cdot (z + \bar{2}) = x]$
15. Note that $+\bar{2}$ appears summing y and z in (14) due to (11).
16. $\text{prime}(n)$ states that n is a prime number.

There is no largest prime

17.

$$(\forall x)(\exists y)[x < y \wedge \text{prime}(y)]$$

Twin Primes Conjecture

18. *There are infinitely many pairs (x, y) such that x and y are both prime and $y = x + 2$.*

19.

$$(\forall x)(\exists y)[x < y \wedge \text{prime}(y) \wedge \text{prime}(y + \bar{2})]$$

20.

$$(\forall x)(\exists y)(\exists z)[x < y \wedge y < z \wedge \text{prime}(y) \wedge \text{prime}(z) \wedge z < y + \bar{3}]$$

21. (19) and (20) are equivalent.

Goldbach Conjecture

22. *Any even number, except 0 and 2, can be written as a sum of two primes.*

23.

$$(\forall x)[(\exists y)[(y + \bar{2}) \cdot \bar{2} = x] \rightarrow (\exists u)(\exists v)[\text{prime}(u) \wedge \text{prime}(v) \wedge u + v = x]]$$

Bounded Gap Theorem

24. *There are infinitely many pairs of prime numbers that differ by 70,000,000 or less.*

25.

$$(\forall x)(\exists y)(\exists z)[x < y \wedge y < z \wedge \text{prime}(y) \wedge \text{prime}(z) \wedge z < y + \overline{70\,000\,000}]$$

26. This theorem was proved by Yitang Zhang in 2013 [3–5].

Final Remarks

27.

$$\mathcal{L}_{NT} = \{0, S, +, \cdot, E, <\}$$

28.

$$\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$$

29.

$$\bar{1} < x \wedge \neg(\exists y)(\exists z)[(y + \bar{2}) \cdot (z + \bar{2}) = x]$$

30.

$$(\forall x)(\exists y)[x < y \wedge \text{prime}(y)]$$

31.

$$(\forall x)(\exists y)(\exists z)[x < y \wedge y < z \wedge \text{prime}(y) \wedge \text{prime}(z) \wedge z < y + \bar{3}]$$

32.

$$(\forall x)(\exists y)[x < y \wedge \text{prime}(y) \wedge \text{prime}(y + \bar{2})]$$

33.

$$(\forall x)[(\exists y)[(y + \bar{2}) \cdot \bar{2} = x] \rightarrow (\exists u)(\exists v)[\text{prime}(u) \wedge \text{prime}(v) \wedge u + v = x]]$$

34.

$$(\forall x)(\exists y)(\exists z)[x < y \wedge y < z \wedge \text{prime}(y) \wedge \text{prime}(z) \wedge z < y + \overline{70\,000\,000}]$$

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [6, 7].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Open Science

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [8, 9].

How to cite this paper?

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/u45y3>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5428990>

Acknowledgements

+ **Center for Open Science**

<https://cos.io>

+ **Open Science Framework**

<https://osf.io>

+ **Zenodo**

<https://zenodo.org>

Agreement

All authors agree with [7].

References

[1] Leary, Christopher C., and Lars Kristiansen. *A friendly introduction to mathematical logic*, 2nd edition, 2015.

<https://knightscholar.geneseo.edu/geneseo-authors/6>

[2] CC. *Creative Commons*. <https://creativecommons.org>

- [3] IAS. “Yitang Zhang’s Spectacular Mathematical Journey.”
<https://www.ias.edu/ideas/2014/zhang-breakthrough>
- [4] Quanta magazine. “Unheralded Mathematician Bridges the Prime Gap.” <https://bit.ly/3v4WcAu>
- [5] Zhang, Yitang. “Bounded gaps between primes.” *Annals of Mathematics* (2014): 1121-1174. <https://bit.ly/3aryBSS>
- [6] Lobo, Matheus P. “Microarticles.” *OSF Preprints*, 28 Oct. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ejrct>
- [7] Lobo, Matheus P. “Simple Guidelines for Authors: Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics.” *OSF Preprints*, 15 Nov. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fk836>
- [8] Lobo, Matheus P. “Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics (OJMP).” *OSF*, 21 Apr. 2020.
<https://doi.org/10.17605/osf.io/6hzyp>
<https://osf.io/6hzyp/files>
- [9] <https://zenodo.org/record/5428990>
- [10] COS. *Open Science Framework*. <https://osf.io>

The Open Mathematics Collaboration

Matheus Pereira Lobo (lead author, mplobo@uft.edu.br)^{1,2}
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4554-1372>

¹Federal University of Tocantins (Brazil)

²Universidade Aberta (UAb, Portugal)